

LEARNING MOTIVATION, SOCIALIZATION ABILITY AND DIGITAL LITERACY: THE IMPACTS OF HYBRID LEARNING OUTCOMES IN AKHLAK TASAWUF STUDY

OLEH: NURDIANA SARI

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Tarbiyah Bustanul Ulum Anak Tuha Lampung Tengah.

Abstract

The demands of learning in the Society 5.0 era have brought the learning system in Indonesia to e-learning and are currently transforming into Hybrid Learning. Hybrid Learning is learning with 50% face-to-face and the other 50% using online. This study aims to determine the relationship between Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability and Digital Literacy with Hybrid Learning Outcomes. This research was conducted on the Akhlak Tasawuf course at the Tarbiyah Bustanul Ulum College of Science, Central Lampung. The sample selected based on the purposive sampling technique was 108 samples and was considered capable of representing the population. Data analysis used correlation tests and F tests with SPSS version 25. The results in this study were the Sig. value. $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, Digital Literacy have a significant relationship with Hybrid Learning Outcomes simultaneously. This is reinforced by the results of the ANOVA test which produced a calculated F value of $125.911 > F$ Table 2.69. In the hybrid learning process, increasing learning motivation, socialization ability and digital literacy is very necessary. The need for cooperation between students, teaching staff and the government in providing socialization in order to produce maximum and responsible learning outcomes.

Keywords: Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, Digital Literacy and Hybrid Learning Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, Hybrid Learning itself began based on the Joint Decree on the Guidelines for Implementing Learning in the 2020/2021 Academic Year, then referred to by the Kemendikbudristek and issued a circular on the implementation of learning with a limited face-to-face system or known as PTMT so that it was reviewed and decided to implement a mixed learning system or Hybrid Learning (Kemendikbud.go.id, 2021). Chen and Chiou (2012), students with Hybrid Learning produce a stronger sense of togetherness compared to traditional classes, this is because the learning style used in Hybrid Learning has a significant effect on learning outcomes.

Hybrid Learning is a blended learning model, which is formally a model that combines face-to-face learning with online learning (Olapiriyakul and Scher, 2006), Rorimpandey and Midun (2021) also stated that Hybrid Learning is a learning system that combines or mixes face-to-face systems and online systems.

This learning strategy can facilitate students in several learning concepts that are not obtained in face-to-face learning systems, because in this Hybrid Learning system, very effective and innovative learning emerges using multimedia devices so as to produce flexible learning strategies, especially in terms of student participation, study materials, time and place of learning.

Thamrin, et.al., (2022) stated that the implementation of Hybrid Learning is effective in improving the achievement of student learning outcomes in assessing creativity and learning independence. This has a higher value compared to a 100% face-to-face learning system. The learning outcomes of Hybrid Learning can answer the demands of learning in the Society 5.0 era or this digitalization era. Hybrid learning has the advantage of being an interesting learning medium and has many types, so that hybrid learning media does not make students bored and tired. This proves that hybrid learning is a learning medium that has its own special features (Swastika and Lukita, 2020).

However, Hybrid Learning is still not effective in all learning, including at elementary and junior high school levels. This is because Hybrid Learning certainly requires devices in the form of network media and of course this requires technical skills to operate the network (Rorimpandey and Midun, 2021), and also requires a focus on digital literacy and responsibility for operating devices and the internet (Asrari, 2022). Hybrid Learning will become increasingly popular, especially for higher education. According to the survey results, it also proves that the results of Hybrid Learning can provide a new, interactive and more enjoyable experience.

They also hope that Hybrid Learning can be implemented in the future, not only during the Covid-19 pandemic. So, some experts conclude that the time will come when 80 to 90% of the total universities in the world will use Hybrid Learning, and it will increase by 30% each year (Thamrin, et.al., 2022). Currently, by creating a new learning space based on hybrid learning, an activity or learning can be attended by all levels, both participants who are on site and those who are far away. So far, many institutions or institutions tend to choose to invest in technological learning spaces because it is considered more effective if a university uses hybrid learning (Raes, et.al., 2020).

Thus, it can be concluded that Hybrid Learning Outcomes are the result of an educational model with a mixed system between traditional face-to-face learning and online learning. Hybrid Learning also combines structured and independent models well so that it produces learning outcomes for each student that are measured using data-based insights.

The success of the hybrid learning model cannot be separated from the role of high motivation from students. Students who have high learning motivation tend to have high achievements, conversely, low learning motivation will also have low learning achievements (Rahman, 2021).

Learning motivation is a mediator that occurs based on stimulation and reaction, or it can also be interpreted as the individual opinion of students about various things, as well as a drive from the student's self for the need to desire to obtain new knowledge (Lin et.al., 2017). Although it is said that hybrid learning is more enjoyable and provides many new experiences, it does not guarantee successful learning outcomes without the motivation and enthusiasm of the students themselves (Munna and Kalam, 2021), here the role of the teacher will dominate as an inspiration in fostering interest, enthusiasm and perseverance in fostering motivation for students (Song, et.al., 2022).

Socialization ability is also very important in creating hybrid learning outcomes. Hybrid learning, which is a mixed model, certainly requires more intense communication between teachers and students or students with other students. This is certainly to avoid miscommunication. Sinta, et. al., (2019) stated that Socialization ability is an ability that is commonly used in maintaining positive relationships in a social interaction from a learning process that aims to get reinforcement or rewards in interpersonal relationships. Petrova, et. al., (2016), the process of socialization has three types, namely positive, negative, reform. Positive socialization can be understood as a blend of knowledge, values, norms and behavior that makes a person successful in interacting with others in a social system in meeting their needs. Negative socialization can be understood as a rejection of the blend of knowledge, values, and norms of behavior that are socially significant, in fact negative socialization of individuals is manifested in the form of deviant behavior. Meanwhile, reform socialization is a process of rejecting the integration of knowledge, values, and behavioral norms that have social meaning, because the individual consciously wants to acquire new knowledge, develop new value orientations and social attitudes. Kuzheleva and Kuzhelev (2021), state that success for students in building socialization is determined through learning motivation, so that Socialization ability is very necessary in learning activities.

With the existence of hybrid learning, the role of digital literacy becomes very important. Not only in terms of how much mastery of technology is obtained by individuals, but also how to find and utilize and be responsible for using the technology (Isnawati, et.al., 2021). Mastery and responsibility in the use of technology will also be more important in hybrid learning (Alvarez, et. al., 2021), although it offers many benefits, it is undeniable that technology can cause boredom and negative assessments (Yuzulia, 2021). Therefore, digital literacy is needed in the hybrid learning process. The positive impact of increasing digital literacy programs is that a person is able to develop all abilities in processing information obtained from the internet (Chan & Chiu, 2017), in addition to positive impacts, digital literacy also has negative impacts, namely with poor understanding of digital literacy cannot improve students' ethics and responsibilities and carry out cyberbullying on social media (Hsu et al., 2018).

In this context, factors that are related to the online learning system still do not have consistent results. The impact of digital literacy and learning motivation on student learning outcomes cannot be fully understood, especially for the hybrid learning method. Moreover, with the socialization ability factor, which has not been explored in previous studies with the results of online and hybrid students. This study was conducted and focused on the Akhlak Tasawuf course at the Bustanul Ulum Tarbiyah College of Science, Central Lampung. STIT BU has one central campus and 4 branch campuses. The geographical location of the campus in the Regency certainly has obstacles in implementing the Hybrid Learning system. One of them is the problem of network and communication. It takes a lot of effort for campus management to ensure that Hybrid Learning can run as it should and Hybrid Learning Outcomes are as expected. Researchers hypothesize that Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, Digital Literacy can have a significant influence on Hybrid Learning Outcomes.

This study aims to generate new insights as a research reference and provide literature in the field of digital learning and researchers hope that this study can be useful in developing online learning strategies. The rest of this research focuses on how Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, Digital Literacy influence Hybrid Learning Outcomes in the Akhlak Tasawuf course.

METHOD

The type of research used in this study is quantitative research. Quantitative research is research that is based on and based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research a certain population or sample, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical in nature with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been set (Sugiyono, 2018). The type of data used in this study is primary data, namely research data obtained directly from the original source (respondents). Primary data is specifically collected through a questionnaire containing questions related to the research being carried out. The purpose of the questionnaire is to obtain information that is relevant to the purpose of the survey, to obtain information with a high level of reliability on a particular phenomenon.

The population in this study were all students and teaching staff at the Tarbiyah Bustanul Ulum College of Central Lampung, totaling 319 people. The sampling procedure used in this study was non-probability with a purposive sampling technique. According to Sugiyono (2018), Purposive sampling is a sampling technique with certain considerations so that the total sample in this study consisted of 108 people. In this study, the variables to be used are the dependent variable (Y), Hybrid Learning Outcomes (Y) and the independent variables Learning Motivation (X1), Socialization Ability (X2) and Digital Literacy (X3). Then for the data analysis technique, this study went through several stages, namely:

- 1) Making descriptive analysis. With an assessment category of 0-25 Less (D), 26-50 is Enough (C), 51-75 is Good (B) and 76-100 is Very Good (A).
 - 2) Conducting a Correlation test using SPSS version 25:
 - a. Bivariate Correlation Test with the basis of assessment:
 - If the Sign value < 0.05 then there is a correlation,
 - If the Sign value > 0.05 then there is no correlation.
- Correlation closeness (Pearson Correlation):
- 0.00 – 0.025 = Very Weak
 - 0.26 – 0.50 = Sufficient
 - 0.51 – 0.75 = Strong
 - 0.76 – 0.99 = Very Strong
 - 1 = Perfect

b. Model Summary, with assessment:

- If the Sign. F Change value <0.05 then there is a significant relationship
- If the Sign. F Change value > 0.05 then there is no significant relationship

Guidelines for the degree of relationship Correlation Coefficient

- 0.00 – 0.199 = Very Low
- 0.20 – 0.399 = Low
- 0.40 – 0.599 = Moderate
- 0.60 – 0.799 = Strong
- 0.80 – 1.00 = Very Strong

c. ANOVA

- If the Sign. < 0.05 then there is a simultan relationship
- If the Sign value. > 0.05 then there is no simultan relationship

- 3) Discussing the research results with previous theories and research
- 4) Conclusions from the research

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Result

The focus of this study will discuss 3 independent variables and 1 dependent variable, namely Learning Motivation (X1), Socialization Ability (X2) and Digital Literacy (X3) which simultaneously have an influence on Hybrid Learning Outcomes (Y) in the Akhlak Tasawuf course at STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung Tengah. Descriptive analysis in this study can be seen in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Hybrid Learning Outcomes	60.91	19.679	108
Learning Motivation	62.83	17.043	108
Socialization Ability	61.28	16.620	108
Digital Literacy	58.97	19.724	108

Source: SPSS 25 Output

In the table above, it can be seen that the number of N samples is 108, the average value of the dependent variable Y (Hybrid Learning) is 60.91 with a standard deviation of 19.679. This value is included in the Good (B) category. Then for the Independent variable X1 (Learning Motivation) has an average value of 62.83 with a standard deviation of 17.043 which means it is also included in the Good (B) category. For variable X1 (Socialization Ability) has an average value of 61.28 with a standard deviation of 16.620

which means it is also included in the Good (B) category, while for the third independent variable, namely X3 (Digital Literacy) has an average value of 58.97 with a standard deviation of 19.724 which means it is also included in the Good (B) category.

For the next stage of Analysis is the Bivariate Correlation Analysis, which can be seen in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Correlations

Correlations					
		Learning Motivation	Socialization Ability	Digital Literacy	Hybrid Learning Outcomes
Learning Motivation	Pearson Correlation	1	.466**	.575**	.754**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	108	108	108	108
Socialization Ability	Pearson Correlation	.466**	1	.586**	.691**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	108	108	108	108
Digital Literacy	Pearson Correlation	.575**	.586**	1	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	108	108	108	108
Hybrid Learning Outcomes	Pearson Correlation	.754**	.691**	.764**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	108	108	108	108

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS 25 Output

Based on Table 2 above, it can be seen that variable X1 (Learning Motivation) has a strong correlation with variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes), this is proven by the Significance value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the Pearson Correlation value of 0.754. For variable X2 (Socialization Ability) with Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes) produces a Significance value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a Pearson Correlation value of 0.691, meaning that variables X2 and Y have a strong correlation relationship. And the third variable, namely X3 (Digital Literacy) with variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes) also has a strong correlation relationship, as evidenced by the Significance value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a Pearson Correlation value of 0.764.

Next, conduct a Model Summary Test, the test results can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Model Summary

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.886 ^a	.784	.778	9.275	.784	125.911	3	104	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Literacy, Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability

Source: SPSS 25 Output

Based on the results of Table 3 Model Summary above, it is concluded that the Sign. F Change value is $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that variables X1 (Learning Motivation), X2 (Socialization Ability) and X3 (Digital Literacy) have a significant relationship to variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes) simultaneously. While the R value (Correlation Coefficient) in Table 3 above is 0.886, it can be concluded that the level of relationship between variables X1 (Learning Motivation), X2 (Socialization Ability) and X3 (Digital Literacy) has a significant relationship to variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes) simultaneously has a Very Strong relationship.

This can also be interpreted that as much as 88.6% of Hybrid Learning Outcomes in the Akhlak Tasawuf course at STIT Bustanul Ulum are influenced by Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, and Digital Literacy while the other 12.4% are influenced by other factors. Other factors could be factors of learning time, attributes in learning and teacher performance. Although these elements are not mentioned in the study, they still have an influence on Hybrid Learning Outcomes, this can be studied in further research. Furthermore, an ANOVA test was conducted, the results are seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32492.931	3	10830.977	125.911	.000 ^b
	Residual	8946.143	104	86.021		
	Total	41439.074	107			
a. Dependent Variable: Hybrid Learning						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Digital Literacy, Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability						

Source: SPSS 25 Output

Based on the results of Table 4 ANOVA above, it can be concluded that variables X1 (Learning Motivation), X2 (Socialization Ability) and X3 (Digital Literacy) simultaneously have a relationship to variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes), as evidenced by the Sign value. $0.000 < 0.05$. This is supported by the results of the F count of $125.911 > F$ Table 2.69, which means that collectively the variables X1 (Learning Motivation), X2 (Socialization Ability) and X3 (Digital Literacy) have a significant effect on variable Y (Hybrid Learning Outcomes). The overall conclusion of this ANOVA test is (Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability and Digital Literacy have a substantial contribution to Hybrid Learning Outcomes in the Akhlak Tasawuf course at STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung Tengah.

B. Discussion

In Table 1, the descriptive analysis shows that the average value of learning motivation is 62.83, which means it is in the Good (B) category. This means that the level of motivation that occurs in hybrid learning of the Akhlak Tasawuf course at STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung is in good condition. This is also supported by the correlation results which show that Learning Motivation has a strong correlation with Hybrid Learning Outcomes and is proven by the Significance value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the Pearson

Correlation value of 0.754. These motivations include the desire that grows from within the student to learn. Not only that, the encouragement given by the lecturer in charge of the course is also important. Although STIT Bustanul Ulum is located in a district that is still limited to internet network issues because only a few providers can enter the area, the enthusiasm and motivation to learn of the students remain good. In the field of Education, encouragement from educators must always provide motivation, because motivation can provide changes in attitudes and behavior, activeness and also interest from students. Because in this era of society 5.0, modern education is mandatory, educators and places of learning cannot underestimate learning motivation and they also have a very big responsibility so that students have learning motivation.

According to Rahman (2021), students who have high learning motivation will also produce high achievements, and vice versa. Therefore, learning motivation affects learning outcomes. Likewise, Andriani (2019) stated that student learning outcomes can be marked by increasing their learning motivation.

Learning motivation is an important element in a good learning system, basically learning is hard work that pushes brain performance to the limit of its ability, therefore the presence of students in class alone does not guarantee that students have a desire to learn, the role of teachers is needed to improve it (Filgona, et. al., 2020). Gibbens (2019) stated that in order for students to be interested and involved in learning and to be able to appreciate the material taught in the long term in the future, the role of teachers in providing learning motivation is very important.

Table 1 shows that the average value of socialization ability is 61.28 and is included in the good category (B). This can be interpreted that the socialization ability of students who take the Akhlak Tasawuf study at STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung Tengah is good. This is also supported by the correlation results which show that socialization ability has a strong correlation with Hybrid Learning Outcomes and is proven by the Significance value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the Pearson Correlation value of 0.691. Socialization abilities, both directly and indirectly, can help students adjust to their environment. In this case, students can adjust to the hybrid learning method. The socialization ability of students who take the Akhlah Sufism course is based on religious, moral, mentally, psychological, physical and environmental factors.

Wahyuni et.al., (2022), during the Covid-19 period, the socialization skills of the Indonesian people in particular were relatively low, the requirement to do all activities at home and the brave learning system were the main causes. Therefore, the less effective brave learning conditions and also the pandemic conditions that began to decline, in 2022 the government issued regulations on hybrid learning. Rahardjo, et.al, (2020), in forming relationships with others, controlling the body, how to speak, how to judge, how to think requires adjustments to oneself. Kuzheleva and Kuzhelev (2021), stated that success for students in building socialization is determined through learning motivation, so that socialization skills are very necessary in learning activities.

Descriptive analysis in Table 1 states that the average value of digital literacy is 58.97 which is also included in the good category (B). This means that the digital literacy obtained by students of the Akhlak Taswuf course at STIT Bustanul Ulum is in good condition. This is also supported by the correlation results which show that digital literacy has a strong correlation with Hybrid Learning Outcomes and is proven by the Signification value (2-tailed) of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the Pearson Correlation value of 0.764. The main thing that needs to be considered in the success of e-learning or hybrid learning is knowledge of the digital device itself, both in terms of technical and non-technical aspects, even in terms of accountability and law of the digital device used. Because, currently in Indonesia in particular has implemented an independent curriculum. Both in formal schools and in universities or called independent campuses. In its implementation, digital literacy plays a very important role in the process of each course. Several previous studies have stated that digital literacy is important for the world of education, whether using traditional learning models, e-learning, or even hybrid learning, and STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung Tengah must be able to keep up with it.

Blau, et.al., (2020), stated that digital literacy is a skill and a competition that is needed to move an unclear information ecosystem into a complex one, therefore digital literacy is a challenge in schools and universities. Students need to understand the meaning of digital literacy technically and psychologically in order to help teachers and schools in making learning successful both face-to-face and hybrid (Arsyad, et.al., 2023). This is in line with research conducted by Asrari (2022) which states that innovation in skills in the era of society 5.0, the world of education needs to utilize technological developments in its learning process. For example, in providing learning materials, an educator must know how to present them because currently electronic publications are very diverse, for example starting from the most popular thing is digital content, e-books, e-journals, e-databases, e-periodicals, and many other online open materials, (Chama, A., and Subaveerapandiyana, A., 2023). According to Arsyad, et al. (2023) the government together with educators need to implement various policies in improving digital literacy, for example by developing digital infrastructure and socializing digital literacy to its citizens.

The limitations of this study include; (a) this study was conducted only on one course, namely Akhlak Sufism, so the results obtained cannot be generalized to all courses. (b) This study uses a quantitative method, so it cannot describe in detail the phenomena in the field. (c) This study was conducted at a university in the Regency area so it cannot cover the description of the phenomena in the urban area. (d) the independent variables used only focus on learning motivation, socialization ability and digital literacy as factors that can influence hybrid learning, while there are other factors that could possibly influence hybrid learning. In this case, the author hopes that further research can be further developed, especially regarding the elements that can influence hybrid learning, for example religious, technical and environmental factors. Then for the method used, the researcher hopes that the data combines quantitative and qualitative methods in order to describe a broader phenomenon.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions that can be drawn from this study are: 1) The average value of Learning Motivation is 62.83, Socialization Ability is 61.28, Digital Literacy is 58.97 and Hybrid Learning is 60.91, meaning that all variables have a good category (B). 2) Sig. Value $0.000 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that Learning Motivation, Socialization Ability, Digital Literacy have a significant relationship to Hybrid Learning Outcomes simultaneously. The R value is 0.886, which means that hybrid learning in this study is 88.6% influenced by learning motivation, socialization ability and digital literacy. This is reinforced by the results of the ANOVA test which produces a calculated F value of $125.911 > F$ Table 2.69, which means that collectively the independent variables have a significant influence on the dependent variable. 3) In the process of e-learning and hybrid learning in the Akhlak Tasawuf course of STIT Bustanul Ulum Lampung Tengah, increasing learning motivation, socialization ability and digital literacy is very necessary. There is a need for cooperation between students, teaching staff and the government in providing socialization in order to produce maximum and responsible learning outcomes.

Reference

- 1) Alvarez, J., Del Angel, D., & Martinez, M. (2021). Edpuzzle and Canvas as distance learning tools during the lockdown. 2021 IEEE International Conference on Engineering Veracruz (ICEV), 1–6.
- 2) Amin, S., Sumarmi, S., Bachri, S., Susilo, S. & Bashith, A. (2020). The Effect of Problem-Based Hybrid Learning (PBHL) Models on Spatial Thinking Ability and Geography Learning Outcomes. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 15(19), 83-94.
- 3) Andriani. (2019). Motivasi Belajar sebagai Determinasi Hasil Belajar Siswa. Manper: Jurnal Pendidikan Perkantoran, 4(1), 6-11.
- 4) Annelies Raes, Loulou Detienne, Ine Windey & Fien Depaepe.(2020). systematic literature review on synchronous hybrid learning: gaps identified. *Learning Environment Research* 23, 269-290.
- 5) Arsyad, Fahma Syariati, and Sukarno. (2023). Digital Literacy and Learning Motivation: Impacts on Online Learning Outcomes in Fiqh Study. *Tadris: Jurnal Keguruan dan Ilmu Tarbiyah* 8 (1): 167-180.
- 6) Ayu Arsari, M. H. A. (2022). The importance of digital literacy to enhance students' ability in English language. *Jambura Journal of English Teaching and Literature*, 3(1), 12–18.
- 7) Arifin, F. (2020). Hybrid Learning sebagai Alternatif Model Pembelajaran. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Profesionalisme Guru Di Era Digital*, 443.
- 8) Bryan H. Chen and Hua-Huei Chiou. (2012). Learning style, sense of community and learning effectiveness in hybrid learning environment. *Interactiv Learning Environment*, 22 (4). 485-496.
- 9) Blau, I., Shamir-Inbal, T., & Avdiel, O. (2020). How does the pedagogical design of a technology-enhanced collaborative academic course promote digital literacies, self-regulation, and perceived learning of students? *The Internet and Higher Education*, 45.
- 10) Chama, A., and Subaveerapandiyana, A. (2023). Digital Literacy Skills of Teachers: A Study on ICT Use and Purposes. *Qeios*. 1-28.
- 11) Chan, B. S. K., & Chiu, T. K. F. (2017). Digital Literacy Learning in Higher Education Through Digital Storytelling Approach. *Journal of International Education Research*, 13(1), 1–16.

- 12) Filgona, Jacob., Sakiyo, John., Gwany, D. M., & Okoronka. A.U. (2020). *Motivation in Learning*. Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies, 10 (4). 16-37.
- 13) Gibbens B. (2019). Measuring Student Motivation an Introductory Biology Class. *The American Biology Teacher*. 81(1), 20-26.
- 14) Hsu, H.-P., Wenting, Z., & Hughes, J. E. (2018). Developing Elementary Students' Digital Literacy Through Augmented Reality Creation: Insights from a Longitudinal Analysis of Questionnaires, Interviews, and Projects. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 57(6), 123-131.
- 15) Isnawati, I., Zamhari, A., Yusuf, M., & Sujoko, I. (2021). Strengthening digital literacy toward students in facing education era 4.0. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Colloquium on Interdisciplinary Islamic Studies, ICIS 2020*, 1-11.
- 16) Kuzheleva and Maxim Kuzhelev. (2021). High school students' socialization features under certain conditions in a secondary school Inessa. *INTERAGROMASH: E3S Web of Conferences* 273, 1-9.
- 17) Ming-Hung Lin., Huang-Cheng Chen and Kuang-Sheng Liu. (2017). A Study of the Effects of Digital Learning on Learning Motivation and Learning Outcome. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 13 (7), 1305-8223.
- 18) Munna, A. S., & Kalam, M. A. (2021). Teaching and learning process to enhance teaching effectiveness: Literature review. *International Journal of Humanities and Innovation (IJHI)*, 4(1), 1–4.
- 19) *Neni Sintia, Cahniyo Wijaya Kuswanto, Meriyati Meriyati.* (2019). Meningkatkan Kemampuan Sosial Anak Usia Dini dengan Model Outbound. *Jurnal Care*, 6(2), hal 1-10.
- 20) Rahardjo, W., Qomariyah, N., Mulyani, I., & Andriani, I. (2020). Social media fatigue pada mahasiswa di masa pandemi COVID-19: Peran neurotisme, kelebihan informasi, invasion of life, kecemasan, dan jenis kelamin. *Jurnal Psikologi Sosial*, 19(2), 142-152.
- 21) Rorimpandey. W.H.F and Midun. H. (2021). Effect of Hybrid Learning Strategy and Self-Efficacy on Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Hunan University Natural Sciences*, 48 (8), 181-189.
- 22) Song, Y., Wei, Y., Shen, Y., & Xu, M. (2022). Evaluation of an online oral English teaching model using big data. *Mobile Information Systems*, 1-10.
- 23) Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan (Pendekatan Kualitatif, Kuantitatif dan R&D)*. Bandung Alfabeta.
- 24) Sulthoniyah, I., Afianah, V. N., Afifah, K. R., & Lailiyah, S. (2022). Efektivitas Model Hybrid Learning dan Blended Learning Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 6(2), 2466–2476.
- 25) Sunarti Rahman. (2021). Pentingnya Motivasi Belajar Dalam Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pendidikan Dasar, "Merdeka Belajar dalam Menyambut Era Masyarakat 5.0."* 289-302.
- 26) Swastika, A., and G. Lukita. (2020). Motivasi Belajar Dalam Pembelajaran Daring Berbasis Learning Management System (LMS) Schoology pada Mata Kuliah Probabilitas." *Indonesian Journal of Instructional*, 1, 9-13.
- 27) Thamrin., Hutasuhut. S., Aditia, R., Putri, F. R. (2022). The Effectiveness of the Hybrid Learning Materials with the Application of Problem Based Learning Model (Hybrid-PBL) to Improve Learning Outcomes during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *IJORER: International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 3(1), 124-134.

- 28) Tatyana N. Petrova., Olga V. Kirillova., Svetlana G. Sokolova., Natalya B. Pugacheva., Alfiya F. Galimullina., Olga G. Maksimova., Tatyana V. Antonova., Vladimir V. Kozhanov. (2016). Education as the Management of Research Universities Students' Socialization. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. 6(S2). 28-33
- 29) Tuapattinaya, P. M. J. (2017). Pengembangan media pembelajaran biologi berbasis hybrid learning untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar siswa pada smp negeri 6 Ambon. *Biosel: Biology Science and Education*, 6(2), 186-192.
- 30) Wahyuni, S., Novitasari, Y., Suharni, S., & Reswita, R. (2023). The effect of digital literacy-based learning on student motivation and socialization ability. *Consilium: Berkala Kajian Konseling dan Ilmu Keagamaan*, 9(2), 26-32.
- 31) Yuzulia, I. (2021). The challenges of online learning during pandemic: Students' voice. *Wanastra: Jurnal Bahasa dan Sastra*, 13(1), 08–12.
- 32) WEB: <https://www.kemdikbud.go.id/main/blog/2020/12/perkuliahan-dapat-dilakukan-secara-tatap-muka-dan-dalam-jaringan-tahun-2021>